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INFLUENCE OF CONTRICAL AND CLEXANE ON SEX HORMONE VALUES IN EARLY PREGNANCY IN THE ABSENCE OF GENITAL INFECTIONS.....10
2. **Khudoyberdiyeva S. Gulrukh**
REDUCING THE INCIDENCE OF POSTOPERATIVE COGNITIVE DYSFUNCTION IN WOMEN UNDERGOING CESAREAN SECTION DURING SPINAL ANESTHESIA AND DRUG SEDATION WITH DESMEDETOMIDINE.....18
3. **Saidjalilova D.Dilnoza, Solieva Kh. Umida**
INFORMATIVITY OF ULTRASONIC DIAGNOSTICS OF ADHESIONS IN THE PELVIC CAVITY IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE.....24

THERAPY

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STUDYING THE COMPONENT COMPOSITION OF THE BODY AT THE EARLY STAGE OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....30
5. **Yusupov T. Jasur, Matlubov M. Mansur.**
IMPROVEMENT OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY THERAPY FOR PATIENTS AFTER CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING.....37
6. **Togayeva M. Barchinoy, Tashkenbayeva N. Eleonora**
STUDY OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE ON THE BACKGROUND OF COVID-19.....42
7. **Tadzhieva U. Nigora, Akhmedova Y. Khalida, Samibayeva Kh. Umida**
VEGF-A VASCULAR ENDOTHELIUM GROWTH FACTOR IN NEW CORONAVIRUS INFECTION COVID-19.....48
8. **Jakbarova A. Mohida, Juraeva A. Mohigul**
CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA.....58
9. **Mukhamadiyeva A. Lola, Umarova S. Saodat, Quldashev F.Sardor**
ACUTE RHEUMATIC FEVER: CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC ASPECTS AT THE PRESENT STAGE.....63

SURGERY

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CLINICAL EFFICACY AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF ENDOVIDEOSURGICAL CORRECTION OF COMBINED ABDOMINAL PATHOLOGY.....71
11. **Batirov A. Bekhzod, Babajanov S. Ahmadjon**
SIMULTANEOUS OPERATIONS IN ABDOMINAL SURGERY (LITERATURE REVIEW).....78
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A DIFFERENTIATED APPROACH TO THE CHOICE OF METHODS FOR MINIMALLY INVASIVE AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF MECHANICAL JAUNDICE OF BENIGN ORIGIN.....83
13. **Babazhanov S. Akhmadjon, Saidov A. Shukhrat**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE TACTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT FOR MECHANICAL JAUNDICE, WHICH HAS DEVELOPED AS A COMPLICATION OF GALLSTONE DISEASE.....90

14. **Holiyev O. Obidjon , Khujabaev T. Safarboy**
QUESTIONS OF ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS.....98
15. **Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Sayinaev K. Farrukh, Yuldashev A. Parda, Abdurakhmanov Sh. Diyor**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF LAPAROSCOPIC AND LAPAROTOMIC INTERVENTIONS FOR POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIA.....106
16. **Nurmurzaev N. Zafar.**
METHODS OF NAVIGATION SURGERY IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS.....116
17. **Allazov A. Salakh, Batirov A. Bekhzod**
MULTI-ORGAN OPERATION: CHOLECYSTECTOMY, INGUINAL GERNIETOMY, PROSTATE ADENOECTOMY, URETRIAL TUNNELIZATION.....122
18. **Dusiyarov M. Mukhammad, Khujabaev T. Safarboy**
CURRENT STATE OF VENTRAL HERNIA SURGERY.....128
19. **Shodmonov A. Akbar, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Askarov A. Pulat.**
ENDOSCOPIC REMISSION OF CLINICAL STEROID-DEPENDENT AND STEROID-RESISTANT FORMS OF NON-SPECIFIC ULCERATIVE COLITIS DURING COMPLEX TREATMENT WITH PLASMAPHERESIS.....136
20. **AHMEDOV Gayrat Keldibaevich, GULAMOV Olimjon Mirzakhitovich, BOBOMURADOV Baxtiyor Murodullayevich, KHUDAYNAZAROV Utkir Rabbimovich**
REFLUX-ESOPHAGITIS: MODERN DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.....144
21. **Akhmedov I. Adkham, Fayazov Dj. Abdulaziz, Karimov R. Doston.**
PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF MOTOR-EVACUATION DYSFUNCTION OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT IN SEVERELY BURNED PATIENTS.....152
22. **Babajanov S. Axmadjon, Abduraxmanov M. Eshonkul, Akhmedov I. Adkham**
SURGICAL TACTICS FOR CHOLELITHIASIS WITH COMPLICATIONS OBSTRUCTIVE JAUNDICE.....158

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

23. **Bakieva Kh. Shakhlo, Djuraev A. Jamolbek, Karimberdiev I. Bakhriddin.**
RESULTS OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH FRONTAL SINUS JOINT INJURIES.....165

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

24. **Akramov R. Akhtam, Rustamova R. Gulnoza.**
DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CHRONIC TONSILLITIS IN CHILDREN AT THE PRESENT STAGE (LITERATURE REVIEW).....174
25. **Lutfullayev U. Gairat, Kobilova Sh. Shakhodat, Adylova Kh. Farzona Yunusova A. Nafosat.**
JUVENILE NASOPHARYNGEAL ANGIOFIBROMA: A CASE REPORT.....185
26. **Lutfullayev U. Gairat, Kobilova Sh. Shakhodat, Adylova Kh. Farzona Yunusova A. Nafosat.**
OTITIS MEDIA WITH EFFUSION IN CHILDREN: A REVIEW.....193

PEDIATRICS

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MARKERS OF INFLAMMATION IN BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN WITH CONSEQUENCES OF PERINATAL DAMAGE TO THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....203
28. **Matlubov M. Mansur, Khudoyberdiyeva S. Gulrukh**
POSTNATAL ADAPTATION PERIOD OF NEWBORNS WHO ARE BORN TO MOTHERS WITH PRE-ECLAMPSIA USING VARIOUS SEDATIVES.....212
29. **Turayeva O. Nafisa**
RISK FACTORS FOR CHILDREN WITH SIGNS OF RICKETS AND CONSEQUENCES OF PERINATAL DAMAGE TO THE NERVOUS SYSTEM.....219

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

30. **Khakimova Z. Sakhiba, Khamdamova K.Bakhora, Ismatov Kh. Shakhboz**
ULTRASOUND DUPLEX SCANNING IN THE DIAGNOSTICS OF NEUROVASCULAR DISORDERS IN LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHIES.....228
31. **Raimova M. Malika, Mamatova A. Shakhnoza, Yodgarova G. Umida.**
THE SPECTRUM OF EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDERS IN POST-STROKE PATIENTS.....237
32. **Kevorkova A. Marina, Magzumova Sh. Shakhnoza**
SOCIAL FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT OF ANXIETYDISORDERS AFTER COVID-19.....244
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COMPARATIVE CLINICAL DYNAMICS OF ANXIETY AND DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS OF PATIENTS WHO SUFFERED COVID-19.....252
34. **Turayev T. Bobir, Ochilov U. Ulug'bek, Sharapova N. Dilfuza**
MODERN APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ACQUIRED MENTAL RETARDATION, EPIDEMIOLOGY OF DEMENTIA, CLINICAL FORMS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....258
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STUDY OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRANSCRANIAL MAGNETIC STIMULATION IN THE TREATMENT OF MOTOR APHASIA AFTER ISCHEMIC STROKE.....266

OPHTHALMOLOGY

36. **Nozimov E. Akhmadjon, Bilalov N. Erkin, Akhmedova M. Sayyora, Yuldashov A. Sarvarkhon.**
ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION OF EXTRAOCULAR MUSCLES IN PATIENTS DIAGNOSED WITH ENDOCRINE OPHTHALMOPATHY.....272
37. **Abdullaeva R. Durdona, Iskandarova A. Malika, Saimbetov A. Salamat**
FEATURES OF THE IMPACT OF GADGETS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF OPHTHALMOPATHIES DEPENDING ON AGE AND SCREEN TIM.....279
38. **YUSUPOV F.Azamat, KHUSANBAEV Sh. Khasanjon ABDULLAEVA I. Saida**
COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETIC RETINOPATHY AND THEIR SOLUTION.....285

ONCOLOGY

39. **Rizayev A. Jasur, Tillyashaikhov N. Mirzagolib, Boyko V. Yelena, Alimov U. Jaloliddin**
A MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH TO ADJUNCTIVE TREATMENT OF COMORBID UROLOGICAL PATHOLOGY IN PROSTATE CANCER.....292

40. **Ismailova A. Jadida, Yusupbekov A. Abror**
THE ROLE OF STUDYING PATHOGENIC STRAINS OF H. PYLORI AND MORPHOLOGICAL STUDIES IN THE EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF GASTRIC CANCER.....300
41. **Shadiev S. Sadulla, Ochilov P. Muhammad.**
STRUCTURE AND LOCALIZATION OF TUMORS AND TUMOR-LIKE FORMATIONS OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN CHILDREN.....307

UROLOGY

42. **Allazov A. Salakh**
NECROTIZING FACCIITIS OF THE EXTERNAL GENITAL ORGANS IN MEN: AN UNSOLVED PROBLEM IN EMERGENCY UROLOGY.....315

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

43. **Rizayev A. Jasur, Ergasheva Y. Munisa**
MEDICAL AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF DISABILITY AFTER NEUROINFECTION IN CHILDREN AND THEIR REHABILITATION.....325
44. **Egamova T. Malika, Dr Vivek, Rasulov Sh. Jamshedjon**
EFFECTIVENESS OF REHABILITATION WITH THE PARTICIPATION OF MOTHERS IN PATIENTS WITH CEREBRAL PALSY.....332
45. **Egamova T. Malika, Ayush Abhinav, Rasulov Sh. Jamshedjon**
METHODS OF ORGANIZING CONTINUOUS REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH CEREBRAL PALSY.....338
46. **Alieva A. Dilfuza**
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE STUDY OF THE IMMUNE SYSTEM IN ATHLETES.....344
47. **Burkhanova L. Gulnoza, Kim A. Olga**
«TEXT NECK» SYNDROME IN CHILDREN PLAYING CHESS.....352
48. **Kim A. Olga**
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF BDNF IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ISCHEMIC STROKE IN YOUNG PEOPLE.....359
49. **Kim A. Olga**
ANALYSIS OF MACRO- AND MICROSTRUCTURAL INDICATORS OF THE BRAIN OF PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE DUE TO ALCOHOL DEPENDENCE.....366

MORPHOLOGY

50. **Bekjanova E Olga, Mannanov J. Javlonbek**
PATHOGENETIC ROLE OF VITAMIN D SYNTHESIS IN THE BODY ON SOMATIC AND DENTAL PATHOLOGY.....373
51. **Makhkamov J. Nasirjon., Nazarov R. Ibragim**
PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE PATHOGENETIC ANGIOGENIC FACTOR OF ASEPTIC NECROSIS OF THE FEMORAL HEAD.....381
52. **Mamadiyarova Dilshoda Umirzokovna**
BLOOD INDICATIONS FOR HYPOXIC FACTOR DURING DIFFERENT PERIODS OF PREGNANCY IN RABBIT FEED WITH IRON AND ZINC ADDED TO THE DAILY DIET AND INSUFFICIENT CALORIE.....387
53. **Zhumanov E. Ziyadulla, Butaev F. Sherzod**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CORONAROCARDIOSCLEROSIS IN THE ELDERLY.....392

54. **Namozov J. Farrukh, Turdiyev R. Mashrab**
 NORMAL MORPHOMETRIC INDICATORS OF THE EPIDIDYMIS OF WHITE
 OUTBREED RATS OF DIFFERENT AGES.....398
55. **Kholhuzhaev I. Farrukh, Mayusupova M. Bivifotima**
 THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SOME MICROELEMENTS AND VITAMIN D IN CHANGES IN
 THE MINERAL COMPOSITION OF BONE TISSUE OF EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS IN
 THE POST-PRODUCTION PERIOD.....405
56. **Khusankhodzhaeva T. Malika, Azimova A. Feruza, Ismailova T. Feruza.**
 MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF UTERINE
 FIBROIDS.....410

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

57. **Xamdamov E.M., Ravshanov Sh.N., Jabborberganov O.D.**
 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SUBTALAR ARTHRODESIS METHODS
 (LITERATURE REVIEW).....421
58. **Khodjanov Yu. Iskandar, Mirzamurodov H.Khabibjon, Novikov I. Konstantin, Klimov
 V. Oleg**
 ON THE ISSUE OF DIAGNOSTICS OF DISTRACTION POTENTIAL OF SEGMENTS OF
 THE LOWER LIMB IN PATIENTS WITH DEFORMATIONS AND SHORTENING OF
 THE LOWER LIMB.....430

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

59. **Bakhtiyorov B. Bahodir, Indiaminov I. Sayit**
 FEATURES OF DAMAGE TO THE STRUCTURE OF THE CHEST, ABDOMEN AND
 PELVIS IN PASSENGERS OF MODERN VEHICLES VICTIMS IN TRANSPORT
 TRAUMA.....439

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

60. **TILYABOV Ikram, USMANOV Ravshan**
 MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE KIDNEYS OF RATS IN DIABETES INDUCED
 BY STREPTOZOTOCIN.....448
61. **Tuxtayev Firdavs Muxiddinovich, Mavlyanov Farxod Shavkatovich, Mavlyanov Shavkat
 Xujamqulovich**
 FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL PICTURE OF UROLITHIASIS IN CHILDREN
 URGENTLY HOSPITALIZED.....458

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MEDICAL AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF DISABILITY AFTER NEUROINFECTION IN CHILDREN AND THEIR REHABILITATION

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ANNOTATION

In the article, it is written in detail that neuroinfections are one of the leading children's infectious diseases, and after neuroinfections, unpleasant consequences occur in half of children, that is, disability with organic symptoms. Similarly, it was explained that part of the structures of the central nervous system are more susceptible to the influence of pathogenic factors, that they are important in the functioning of the nervous system, and that they depend on the development of the brain depending on the age of the child.

The article shows the main causes of disability that develops after neuroinfections, risk factors, and measures to prevent children's disability, which are the main problems of the children's health care system. As one of the most effective measures for early detection and prevention of disabling neuroinfections, the registry of rare neuroinfections is detailed, as well as rehabilitation of neuroinfections.

Key words: children's disability, medical and social care, neuroinfection, encephalitis, rehabilitation.

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BOLALARDA NEYROINFEKTSIYADAN KEYIN NOGIRONLIKNING TIBBIY VA IJTIMOYIY JIHATLARI VA ULARNI REABILITATSIYA QILISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada neyroinfektsiyalar bolalar yuqumli kasalliklari orasida etakchi o'rinlardan birini egallashi hamda neyroinfektsiyalardan so'ng bolalarning yarmida noxush oqibatlar kelib chiqishi, y'ani organik alomatlar bilan nogironlik kelib chiqishi haqida batafsil yozilgan. Shuningdek, markaziy asab tizimi tuzilmalarining bir qismi patogen omillar ta'siriga ko'proq moyil bo'lishi, asab tizimi faoliyatida muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligi, bola yoshiga bog'liq bosh miya rivojlanishiga bog'liqligi yoritilgan. Maqolada neyroinfektsiyalardan so'ng rivojlanadigan nogironlikning asosiy sabablari, xavf omillari, bolalar salomatligini muhofaza qilish tizimining asosiy muammolari bo'lgan bolalar nogironligining oldini olish choralari ko'rsatilgan. Nogironlikka olib keladigan neyroinfektsiyalarni erta aniqlash va oldini olishning eng samarali chora-tadbirlaridan biri sifatida kam uchraydigan neyroinfektsiyalar reestri, shuningdek, neyroinfektsiyalar rehabilitatsiyasi batafsil yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: bolalar nogironligi, tibbiy-ijtimoiy yordam, neyroinfektsiya, ensefalit, rehabilitatsiya.

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МЕДИКО-СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИНВАЛИДНОСТИ ПОСЛЕ НЕЙРОИНФЕКЦИИ У ДЕТЕЙ И ИХ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье подробно написано, что нейроинфекции являются одними из ведущих детских инфекционных заболеваний, а после нейроинфекций у половины детей возникают неприятные последствия - инвалидность с органическими симптомами. Аналогичным образом было объяснено, что часть структур ЦНС более подвержена влиянию патогенных факторов, что они имеют важное значение в функционировании нервной системы и что от них зависит развитие мозга в зависимости от возраст ребенка.

В статье показаны основные причины инвалидности, развивающейся после нейроинфекций, факторы риска, а также меры профилактики детской инвалидности, которые являются основными проблемами системы детского здравоохранения. В качестве одной из наиболее эффективных мер раннего выявления и профилактики инвалидизирующих нейроинфекций детализированный регистр редких нейроинфекций, а также реабилитация нейроинфекций.

Ключевые слова: детская инвалидность, медико-социальная помощь, нейроинфекция, энцефалит, реабилитация.

Bugungi kunga kelib, bolalar populyatsiyasidagi nogironlik darajasi aholi salomatligi holatining asosiy detektorlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Nogironlik holati bolaning o'sishi va rivojlanishining doimiy buzilishiga olib keladigan sog'lig'ining somatik yoki psixo-nevrologik nuqsoni tufayli yuzaga keladi [1].

Bolalar nogironligi asosan ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy jihatlar, fan va texnika yutuqlari bilan oldindan belgilanadi. Bolalar salomatligini muhofaza qilish bo'yicha davlat tizimlarining faoliyati, shuningdek, bemorlarning hayot sifatini yaxshilashga qaratilgan tibbiy xizmat va sog'liqni saqlash tizimidagi islohotlar, tibbiy yordam ko'rsatishda xususiylashtirilgan tibbiyotni joriy etish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Sog'liqni saqlash tizimida nogiron bolalarga g'amxo'rlik qilish, shuningdek, bolalar nogironligining oldini olishga qaratilgan profilaktika choralari muhim o'rinni egallaydi [4].

Bolalar populyatsiyasidagi nogironlik tarkibida ruhiy kasalliklar, markaziy va periferik asab tizimining patologiyasi, tug'ma nuqsonlar etakchi o'rinni egallaydi, bu bolalar nogironligini keltirib chiqaradigan barcha patologik holatlarning 2/3 qismini tashkil qiladi [3, 7].

Neyroinfektsiyalar bolalarning yuqumli kasalliklari orasida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Neyroinfektsiyalarning qoldiq davrida bolalarning yarmida doimiy organik alomatlar bilan

nogironlik rivojlanadi [11, 12]. Neyroinfektsiyalarning qoldiq davrida bola yoshiga bog'liq bosh miya rivojlanishiga ontogenetik bosqichlari kechikishi kuzatilganda aniqlanishi mumkin [11].

Ko'pchilik tadqiqotchilar neyroinfektsiyalarning og'ir oqibatlarini mavjudligi sababli reabilitatsiyaga bo'lgan talabni va kasallikning o'tkir davrida reabilitatsiya tadbirlarini o'tkazish muhimligini ta'kidlaydilar, chunki bu tadbirlarni erta boshlash reabilitatsiya samaradorligini belgilab, asoratlarning oldini olishga va nogironlikning kamayishiga olib keladi [13].

Neyroinfektsiyalar oqibatiga bag'ishlangan nashrlarda nevrologik etishmovchilik va kognitiv holatlarning rivojlanish mexanizmlari haqida etarli ma'lumot yo'qligi, meta-tahlillarning kamligi va xulosalar chiqarishdagi qiyinchiliklar qayd etilgan [14-17]. Neyroinfektsiyalar orasida bemorlarning hayot sifatini pasaytiradigan uzoq muddatli nevrologik oqibatlar 25-63% ga etadi [17, 18].

Neyroinfektsiyalar oqibatini o'rganishda mualliflar vaksinalarning roli, premorbid fon, kasalxonaga yotqizish muddatlari, antimikrobiyal terapiyani boshlash va tanlash vaqti, glyukokortikoidlar, ovqatlanish holati va suvsizlanish muammolariga e'tibor berishadi [14, 19, 22]. Afsuski, neyroinfektsiyalar oqibatini davolashda reabilitatsiyaning asab tizimiga ta'siri deyarli muhokama qilinmaydi. Neyroinfektsiyalarga chalingan bolalarni reabilitatsiya qilish va va bunday bolalarni olib borish turli omillarga bog'liq. Neyroinfektsiyalarga chalingan bolalar quyidagi qoldiq o'zgarishlar kuzatiladi: kognitiv buzilishlar, turli vegetativ buzilishlar, diqqat etishmasligining giperaktiv turdagi buzilishi, markaziy yoki periferik parezlar, koordinatsiya va nutqning buzilishi, epilepsiyaning turli shakllari va boshqalar [9]. Meningokokk meningiti bilan kasallanish holatining 868 ta ko'rinishini meta-tahlil qilishda [17], ularning 18 foizida eshitish qobiliyatini yo'qotish (5,4%), ruhiy buzilishlar (5,4%), ayrim hollarda buyrak usti bezi va buyrak funksiyasining buzilishi (2,6%) tutilib gapirish (2,5%). seroz meningit bilan kasallangan bolalarda Reabilitatsiya davrida serebrosteniya (40-85% hollarda) va "ishchi xotira" ning pasayishi (24%) qayd etilgan. 20-40% hollarda muammolar olti oygacha davom etadi. Ayrim hollarda neyroinfektsiyalardan so'ng gipertenziv sindrom (13%), diensefalik ko'rinishlar (16%) va fokal simptomlar (10%) ham kuzatiladi. Kasallikdan bir yil o'tgach, asteno-nevrotik (35%) va gipertonik (19%) sindromlar, simptomatik epilepsiya (3%) davom etishi mumkin [9]. Yuqumli ensefalitdan keyin bosh miyada sezilarli funktsional pasayish yuz berishi mumkin [24, 25]. Ensefalit bilan og'rigan bemorlarning deyarli 80% izida neyropsikologik oqibatlar kuzatiladi. Diqqat va xulq-atvorning buzilishi, emotsional buzilishlar kasallikning o'tkir bosqichi tugaganidan keyin uch yil davomida shakllanadi [26, 25].

AQShda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, 2004-2008 yillarda kana ensefaliti bilan kasallanishdan so'ng 55 bolaning 37 tasida 2-5 yildan keyin kognitiv nuqsonlar, bosh og'rig'i, charchoq va asabiylashish aniqlanilgan. Ota-onalar yoki o'qituvchilar tomonidan o'tkazilgan so'rov natijalariga ko'ra, bolalarning uchdan biridan ko'prog'i xatti-harakatlar, motivatsiya va ish xotirasi bilan bog'liq muammolarga duch kelishgan [27]. Shunga o'xshash ma'lumotlar Shvetsiya, Xitoy va Rossiyada o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarida ham mavjud. Kana ensefalitining erta yoki kech oqibatlarini ko'rinishidagi diqqat etishmasligi, giperaktivlik ko'rinishidagi kognitiv buzilishlar bolalarning 50 foizida aniqlanilgan [27-29]. Shuningdek, neyroinfektsiyalardan so'ng rivojlanadigan qoldiq o'zgarishlar orasida muhim muammolardan biri postinfeksion epilepsiyadir. Ensefalitlarning o'tkir davrida konvulsiv sindrom kasallangan bolalarning yarmidan ko'pida paydo bo'lishi mumkin [30]. Bosh miya bilan bog'liq asosiy muammolarga qo'shimcha ravishda, postinfeksion epilepsiya bilan og'rigan bemorlarda depressiya va o'z o'zidan tashvishlanish xavfi ortadi [31]. 1980-2008 yillarda Daniya tadqiqotchilari tomonidan o'tkazilgan umummilliy aholi kohort tadqiqoti natijalariga ko'ra, aholi orasida ta'lim darajasi ning pastligi, iqtisodiy yetishmovchilik, ish bilan ta'minlanishning sezilarli darajada qisqarishi va bolalik davrida neyroinfeksiya bilan kasallangan kattalardagi nogironlik pensiyasiga bo'lgan ehtiyojning ortishi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan [32].

Kanadalik olimlar tomonidan yuqumli ensefalitdan keyin reabilitatsiya bo'yicha 12 737 manbadan olingan 20 ta tadqiqotning meta-tahlilini o'tkazishga urinishgan. To'qqizta tadqiqotda kognitiv terapiya, beshtasida xulq-atvor terapiyasi, ikkitasida fizika terapiyasi va to'rttasida yaxlit reabilitatsiyani ko'rib chiqishgan. Afsuski, har bir holatda tekshiriluvchilar orasida kuzatuv maydonining kichikligi (25 bemordan ko'p bo'lmagan), klinik va uslubiy geterogenlik tufayli kutilgan meta-tahlilni amalga oshirib bo'lmadi [33, 34]. Boshqa bir tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, kattalar va

bolalarda ensefalit bilan kasallanishdan olti oy o'tgach, hayot sifati, ayniqsa bolalar kohortasida pasayadi [35, 36].

Herpetik ensefalit bilan og'riq bolalarda yoshga bog'liq quyidagi xususiyatlar qayd etilgan: bir yoshgacha - polimorf nevrologik ko'rinishlar (tetraparez, gidrosefalik sindrom, simptomatik epilepsiya, aqliy zaiflik), 1-3 yoshli bolalarda – motorik rivojlanishning kechikishi, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutq rivojlanishining buzilishi va kechikishi - ataksiya, nevroz va nevrozga o'xshash holatlar; maktab o'quvchilarida - hissiy-ixtiyoriy sohaning buzilishi, gipotalamik kasalliklar va intellektual holatlar rivojlangan [9].

Yuqumli qo'zg'atuvchilar tomonidan chaqirilgan kasalliklarda bolalarda markaziy asab tizimining demyelinizatsiya qiluvchi fokal o'zgarishlari 30% hollarda qoldiq nevrologik etishmovchilikni shakllantirishi yoki 20% hollarda og'ir polisindromik nevrologik etishmovchilik shakllanishi bilan progressiv ko'rinishga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Bolalarda bosh miya va periferik asab tizimining yuqumli kasalliklari orasida miyelopatiya, miyelopolineyropatiya, polineyropatiya, yuz nevropatiyasi va poliradikulopatiya shaklida uchraydi [9].

Neyroinfeksiya bilan kasallangan bolalarni rehabilitatsiya choralari sifatida ularda jismoniy faollikni stimullash, mashqlar terapiyasi, massaj, nutq funksiyalarini tiklash, psixoterapiya, yotoq yaralar, kontrakturalar, pnevmoniya va trombotik asoratlarning oldini olish kabi choralarni taklif qilishadi. Shuningdek, motor harakatining individual tarkibiy qismlarini tiklash, oddiy do'stona harakatlarni tiklash, bo'g'imlararo o'zaro ta'sirning turli xil variantlarini o'rgatish va vosita ko'nikmalarini tiklash bilan bosqichma-bosqich rehabilitatsiyadan foydalanish taklif etiladi.

Miyelit, poliomielitda periferik parezlar bo'lsa, yallig'lanish o'zgarishlarini bartaraf etish, trofik jarayonlarni yaxshilash uchun elektr stimulyatsiyasi, ozokerit qo'llash, gimnastik jismoniy mashqlar (umumiy rivojlanish va nafas olish), zararlangan oyoq-qo'l uchun maxsus mashqlar, gidrokineziterapiya buyuriladi.

Og'riq va vegetativ-trofik kasalliklarni bartaraf etish, vosita funksiyalarini tiklash, ikki va to'rt kamerali vannalar, diadinamik oqimlar, sinusoidal modulyatsiyalangan oqimlar, interferentsiya oqimlari, ultratovush yoki ultrafonoforez, o'zgaruvchan magnit maydon, ozokerit ilovalari, magnit lazer terapiyasi tavsiya etiladi. Kinesiterapiya, vosita funksiyalarini tiklashda robot terapiyasi, vertikalizatorlardan foydalanish, dinamik parapodiumlar, dinamik propriozeptiv tuzatish, nutq terapiyasi usullari, biofeedback terapiyasi ko'rib chiqiladi [9].

Xulosa. Erta bolalik davrida immuniteti to'liq shakllanmagan bolalarda neyroinfeksiyalarga chalinish xavfi yuqori bo'lib, bu holat ularda og'ir asoratlar kelib chiqishiga sabab bo'ladi. Shu bois, neyroinfeksiya bilan kasallangan bolalarni har tomonlama rehabilitatsiya qilish va dinamik monitoringini o'tkazish zarurati bolalar sog'lig'ini to'liq tiklash shartlaridan biri sifatida qaraladi.

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